

The impact of segmentation uncertainty on radiomics reproducibility to segmentation and acquisition variability in kidney MRI

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SUMMARY:

Segmentation and acquisition variability are known to affect radiomics robustness. This study explores whether incorporating an analysis of segmentation uncertainty into the radiomic pipeline can automatically mitigate these limitations, extracting features only from confidently segmented regions.

INTRODUCTION:

Radiomics aims at quantitatively characterizing medical images through high-throughput extraction of image features [1]. Despite its potential in precision medicine, radiomics encounters stability challenges due to the variability and uncertainty present in each step of its pipeline [2]. Radiomic studies have highlighted that a significant issue arises from segmentation variability and acquisition variability, with the latter having a predominant impact on radiomics robustness. [3]

This study, which is part of a larger project [4], explores whether quantifying segmentation uncertainty can offer an automated approach to effectively address these limitations. Specifically, we examine whether extracting features solely from confidently segmented regions enhances radiomics robustness compared to extracting features from the entire segmented regions without accounting for segmentation uncertainty.

METHODS:

Dataset.

The dataset comprises T2-weighted kidney MRI scans obtained from a public source [5]. It includes scans from 60 individuals, with the relative kidney masks manually segmented, assumed as Ground Truth (GT). Among them, 30 subjects had Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD), while the other 30 were Healthy Control individuals (HC). Ten subjects (5 HCs and 5 CKDs) that underwent scanning five times within a single session were here used as test data and for radiomic analysis.

Automatic segmentation and uncertainty estimation.

Kidneys segmentation was performed using a 2D U-Net [6] model. 50 MRI volumes, partitioned in 80% training and 20% validation data, underwent pre-processing according to the pipeline proposed in [5], with data augmentation to prevent overfitting. The model employed Adam Optimizer and Dice score loss function. The mean Dice score on testing data was 0.92 (0.93 for HCs and 0.92 for CKDs).

To estimate segmentation uncertainty, a Bayesian U-Net approach employing Monte Carlo Dropout (MCD) was adopted [7]. Starting from the deterministic U-Net architecture, dropout layers were introduced and kept active during both training and inference. During inference, 50 MCD samples were generated through 50 forward passes across the network, producing stochastic predictions. The Mean

Prediction segmentation mask (MP) was computed as their pixel-wise mean. An overview of the network architecture is provided in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Bayesian U-Net architecture.

To delineate masks reflecting different Levels of Confidence in segmentation (CL masks), thresholds for agreement among the 50 MCD samples were established, ranging from 0.1 to 1 with a 0.1 step size. The pipeline for estimating the different masks is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. A. Workflow to define masks for radiomic analysis. MRI and GT are available in the dataset. Starting from the input MRI, 50 MCD segmentations are obtained from the network. Their pixel-wise mean defines the MP mask. By establishing thresholds over the agreement of the 50 segmentations, CL masks are defined. $CL_{th=0.1}$ represents the regions classified as kidney by at least 10% of the 50 MCD samples. Similarly, $CL_{th=1.0}$ represents the regions identified as kidney by all the 50 segmentations. **B.** Reproducibility analysis without accounting for segmentation uncertainty. **C.** Reproducibility analysis when considering segmentation uncertainty. This analysis is repeated for each segmentation confidence level th .

Reproducibility Analysis.

Radiomic features were extracted using Pyradiomics package [8] in Python from GT, MP and CL masks for all test acquisitions. Reproducibility to segmentation variability was assessed by estimating Intra-class Correlation Coefficient (ICC) type 3 between manually and automatically delineated kidney regions (ICC_S), whereas reproducibility to acquisition variability was estimated by ICC type 2 among the five scan repetitions per subject on the kidney mask (ICC_A). This analysis was performed firstly by considering the MP mask to compute ICC_S and GT mask for ICC_A , and secondly by considering CL masks, at different thresholds, for both ICC computation, to evaluate the effect of including confidence information (see Figure 2).

For each of the two analyses, features were classified in 4 classes: class 1 when ICC_S and ICC_A are ≥ 0.8 ; class 2 when ICC_S is ≥ 0.8 and ICC_A is < 0.8 ; class 3 as the opposite of class 2; class 4 when both ICC_S and ICC_A are < 0.8 .

Analyses were performed considering all subjects together, and for HC and CKD subjects separately.

RESULTS:

Figure 3. Results without accounting for segmentation uncertainty, considering all subjects (A), CKD subjects (B) and HC subjects (C) separately.

Figure 3 illustrates that without considering uncertainty information, most of the features fall in class 4, indicating poor robustness to segmentation and acquisition variability. Features in class 1 primarily correlate with volume measures.

In Figure 4, as segmentation confidence increases, the number of features classified as class 4 decreases, while those in class 3 increases.

Furthermore, when considering only HC subjects and accounting for segmentation confidence, both ICC_S and ICC_A increase, and thus more features are included in class 1.

Figure 4. Results when evaluating segmentation uncertainty, considering all subjects (A), CKD subjects (B) and HC subjects (C) separately.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION:

This study aimed to address the challenge of reproducibility in radiomic features due to variability in image segmentation and acquisition. To this aim, we proposed an automatic approach based on segmentation confidence evaluation. Results show that while acquisition variability consistently affects outcomes, segmentation variability is more pronounced in CKDs due to lower accuracy. Extracting features from the most confident regions reduces acquisition variability for both HCs and CKDs, and decreases segmentation variability only for HCs, remarking the importance of accurate segmentation. Therefore, integrating a segmentation uncertainty evaluation step into the radiomics workflow appears promising to enhance radiomic analysis robustness.

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